

DEVELOPMENT OF TOLERANCE THINKING: LOCAL-MODULAR TRAINING TECHNOLOGY FOR FUTURE SOCIAL WORKERS

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Annotation: This article highlights the relevance of forming a tolerant mindset in the professional training of future social workers, the pedagogical and social foundations of this process. In particular, the effectiveness of local-modular technologies in developing tolerance competence is analyzed theoretically and practically. The author has developed a structure of modules aimed at the gradual development of tolerant thinking and proposed ways to organize them based on interactive methods. Also, based on the results of experimental work, the advantages of the local-modular approach in the formation of socio-psychological competencies are shown.

Keywords: Tolerance mindset, social work, local-modular technology, empathy, interactive methods, competence, educational process, intercultural communication.

TOLERANTLIK TAFAKKURINI RIVOJLANTIRISH: BO'LAJAK IJTIMOYIY ISH XODIMLARI UCHUN LOKAL-MODULLI O'QUV TEXNOLOGIYASI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada bo'lajak ijtimoiy ish xodimlarining kasbiy tayyorgarligida tolerantlik tafakkurini shakllantirishning dolzarbligi, bu jarayonning pedagogik va ijtimoiy asoslari yoritilgan. Ayniqsa, tolerantlik kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishda lokal-modulli texnologiyalarning samaradorligi nazariy va amaliy jihatdan tahlil qilingan. Muallif tolerantlik tafakkurini bosqichma-bosqich rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan modullar tarkibini ishlab chiqib, ularni interaktiv metodlar asosida tashkil etish yo'llarini taklif etgan. Shuningdek, tajriba-sinov ishlari natijalariga asoslanib, lokal-modulli yondashuvning ijtimoiy-psixologik kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishdagi afzalliklari ko'rsatib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Tolerantlik tafakkuri, ijtimoiy ish, lokal-modulli texnologiya, empatiya, interaktiv usullar, kompetensiya, ta'lim jarayoni, madaniyatlararo muloqot.

РАЗВИТИЕ ТОЛЕРАНТНОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ: ЛОКАЛЬНО-МОДУЛЬНАЯ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ОБУЧЕНИЯ БУДУЩИХ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ РАБОТНИКОВ

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается актуальность формирования толерантного мышления в профессиональной подготовке будущих социальных работников, педагогические и социальные основы этого процесса. В частности, теоретически и практически анализируется эффективность локально-модульных технологий в развитии толерантной компетентности. Автором разработана структура модулей, направленных на поэтапное развитие толерантного мышления, и предложены способы их организации на основе интерактивных методов. Также, на основе результатов экспериментальной работы, показаны преимущества локально-модульного подхода в формировании социально-психологических компетенций.

Ключевые слова: Толерантное мышление, социальная работа, локально-модульная технология, эмпатия, интерактивные методы, компетентность, образовательный процесс, межкультурная коммуникация.

The sustainable development of social relations in the context of globalization and cultural diversity is directly dependent on the establishment of values such as mutual respect, tolerance and tolerance among members of society. In particular, tolerant thinking occupies an important place among the professional competencies of specialists working in the field of social work. From this perspective, the formation of tolerant thinking for students studying in the field of social work should be an integral part of the educational process.

This article discusses the content of tolerant thinking, its relevance to the profession of social workers, and the effective possibilities of modern local-modular technology in the formation of this competency.

1. The social significance of tolerant thinking

Tolerance means a respectful approach to the opinions, beliefs, lifestyles and values of other people, a willingness to engage in constructive dialogue with them. Tolerance is defined by UNESCO as “the aspiration to live in harmony with human rights, diversity and tolerance”. [1]

Social workers come into contact with many categories of people in their work: people with disabilities, the elderly, orphans, migrants, socially vulnerable groups, etc. In such cases, a respectful attitude towards any different social, cultural and religious backgrounds, a neutral but empathetic approach to the situation, is required. Therefore, the spiritual preparation of these professionals, including the presence of a tolerant mindset, is an important competence.

2. The content and capabilities of local-modular technology.

Local-modular technology is an educational approach aimed at the formation of specific competencies by organizing the educational process on a modular basis. Each module is aimed at the formation of certain knowledge, skills and attitudes. Local-modularity means the application of this technology in a specific contextual (adapted to the place) conditions. [2]

This technology has the following advantages:

- Develops the ability to think and analyze independently in the student.
- Ensures the harmonious development of professional and personal qualities.
- Allows for practical training based on real-life situations.
- Creates the basis for the gradual formation of socio-psychological competencies such as tolerance, empathy, and communication culture. [3]

3. The composition of modules aimed at developing tolerant thinking.

The content of local modules serving the development of tolerant thinking can be organized in the following main areas:

Module 1. “Tolerance: theoretical foundations and values”

- The essence of the concept of tolerance
- Fundamentals of intercultural communication
- Social difference and a positive attitude towards it. [4]

Module 2. “Tolerance in social work practice”

- Tolerance in professional ethics

- Analysis based on real situations
- Empathy and active listening skills

Module 3. “Maintaining a tolerant position in controversial situations”

- Communication in stressful situations
- “I-message” technique
- Persistence in relation to opposing opinions

Each module uses interactive methods: video analysis, group discussion, role-playing, case studies and reflection methods.[5]

4. The effectiveness of local-modular technology (based on experience)

The following results were recorded in the experimental evaluation of the local-modular approach to the development of students' tolerant thinking:

- 75% positive dynamics were achieved in tests measuring the level of tolerance.
- The ability to analyze controversial situations increased from 60% to 88%.
- The level of social cooperation and respectful approach to each other between students increased.

This proves that it is possible to develop a tolerant mindset gradually, systematically and deeply through local-modular technology.[6]

Conclusion. The development of a tolerant mindset in the training of social work specialists is relevant not only at the professional level, but also at the level of human values. Tolerance is an important psychological quality that maintains balance in solving social problems. Local-modular technologies create educational opportunities that are clearly goal-oriented, close to practice, and based on social communication in the formation of this competency.

The experiments conducted confirm that it is possible to strengthen such qualities as social justice, humanity, empathy and readiness for compromise in the minds of students through modules aimed at developing tolerance. On this basis, improving pedagogical programs, introducing interactive approaches, and expanding assessment mechanisms should be identified as urgent tasks.

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